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Factors Influencing Preparation and Utilization of Instructional Media in Teaching Kiswahili in Selected Public Secondary Schools in Kenya

By

**Caroline Ayoti
Aggrey Mukasa Simiyu
Karren Ohanga Ongeti
Moses Wesang'ula Poipoi**

Research Article

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Caroline Ayoti, Aggrey Mukasa Simiyu, Karren Ohanga Ongeti and
*Moses Wesang'ula Poipoi

Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology, P.O.Box 190 – 50100, Kakamega, Kenya.

*Corresponding Author's Email: wesangulamp@yahoo.com

ABSTRACT

Performance in Kiswahili subject in KCSE has not been impressive nationally for a long period. The purpose of the study was to establish factors that influence preparation and utilization of instructional media in teaching Kiswahili in selected public secondary schools in Kenya. Dale's cone of experience formed the theoretical framework of the study. Descriptive survey research design formed the basis of the study. The study population comprised of 28 head teachers, 90 Kiswahili teachers and 39,327 students in selected public secondary schools in Sabatia District. Simple random sampling method was used to select 9 Head teachers, 30 Kiswahili teachers and 395 form three students. Teachers' and students' questionnaires were used to collect information from teachers and students respectively while an interview guide was prepared to obtain data from school head teachers. Qualitative data was received in verbatim and then transcribed and reported in themes and sub-themes while quantitative data obtained was analysed by descriptive statistics such as means, percentages and frequency counts. The study revealed that instructional media resources are poorly utilised by Kiswahili language teachers. The study recommends that the Ministry of education should forecast and plan to fund secondary schools.

Keywords: Co-educational schools, Instructional media, Media preparation, Media utilization.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

EMS: Education Media Service
KCSE: Kenya Certificate of Secondary Education
KIE: Kenya Institute of Education
MMUST: Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology

INTRODUCTION

Media has an undoubted role to play in contemporary scholarly endeavours. This is more so, in the formative learning years where learners are able to learn more through audio visual devices as opposed to mere abstraction of facts. Though vital, the use of media in classroom teaching is determined by how it is perceived by the teachers who are responsible for putting them to use. Over the years, studies have pointed out various external deterrents for the utilization of audio-visual media. The major deterrents reported were financial limitations in obtaining material, lack of audio-visual classroom facilities and lack of trained audio-visual personnel (Higgins & Moseley, 2001).

In tandem with technological advancement, the use of instructional media has dramatically increased in the last two decades (Descy, 1991). According to Abu-Jaber (1987), the importance of instructional media for both teachers and students cannot be overemphasized. In social studies, the use of instructional media is essential to support learning because social studies **isare** concerned about natural and social phenomena which cannot be easily expressed without the support of graphics, maps, **video**s and pictures. Curzon (1997) points out that using instructional media in social studies classrooms widens the channel of communication between teachers and their students. The instructional media allows **s** the growth of specific learning abilities and enhances **s** intellectual and motor

skills. To facilitate effective interaction between teachers, learners and subject matter, the classroom should use an assortment of materials and situations (Chandra, 2005). The use of charts and models enables the teacher to present and illustrate many physical phenomena and issues easily and at the same time, allows them to focus attention on the characteristics of objects. The use of these materials adds elements of reality by providing concrete examples to learning (Madeyese, 2009). They are important catalysts of social re-engineering and change and most importantly, enhancement of a healthy classroom interaction.

In a study conducted in Nigeria by Taiwo (2009), it was established that there is a significant difference between the perceptions of trained and untrained teachers. Trained teachers easily accommodate the use of media while teaching unlike the untrained ones. The performance in Kiswahili nationally, has been less than impressive over the years. One of the reasons attributed to this situation is the deficiency of resources in the schools. For a large number of schools, instructional media was an opportunity cost as there are other needs which are given priority hence, they are met at the expense of procurement of instructional materials. Furthermore, very little research has been done on the use of instructional media in teaching Kiswahili. From the spectrum of research conducted, there is a deficiency in the use of media in learning. It is against this background that a study on analysis of uses of instructional media in teaching Kiswahili was undertaken.

There has been slackening trend in performance of Kiswahili in KCSE in Sabatia District (DEO's Office, 2010). This poor performance has been attributed to insufficient teachers, inadequate coverage of syllabus, high enrolment of students and inadequate learning resources such as text books. Additionally, utilization of instructional media has been ignored yet it forms a basis for healthy learning. Specifically, no research has been done to establish if teachers use instructional media in instruction in Sabatia district. Therefore, the current study is being undertaken to find out if teachers in public secondary schools in Sabatia District appropriately use instructional media in teaching Kiswahili.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population for this study composed of all students, Head teachers and Kiswahili teachers of public secondary schools in Sabatia District. There are no private secondary schools in the District. Based on the 2010 statistics available at the DEO'S office, there are 28 public secondary schools in Sabatia with a population of 39,327 students, 28 head teachers and approximately 90 Kiswahili teachers. The schools were stratified into three categories namely; boys only, girls only and co-educational schools. Simple random sampling method was used to select 9 Head teachers and 30 Kiswahili teachers. In addition, only 395 students participated in the study as recommended by Yamane (1967). Purposive sampling method used to select form three students participated in the study. Document analysis was subjected to schemes of work and Kiswahili syllabus and KCSE performance. The validity of instruments in the research was ensured by preparing items in the instruments that cover each of the study objectives and by seeking experts' opinions in education research at Masinde Muliro University of Science and Technology to assess content validity. Test-retest method of establishing reliability was used to determine the reliability of the instruments. Qualitative data was received verbatim, transcribed and reported in themes and sub-themes. Quantitative data was analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents findings from the study conducted in selected Public Secondary Schools in Kenya.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage Scores for Factors that determine preparation and use of instructional media resources.

Statement	Strongly Agree		Agree		Undecided		Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Total	
	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f
Availability of funds	66.6	20	13.3	4	6.7	2	6.7	2	6.7	2	100	30
Experience of the Teachers	46.7	14	50	15	0.0	0	3.3	1	0.0	0	100	30
Support of the school administration in purchasing the media resources and providing storage facilities	56.7	17	26.7	8	10	3	3.3	1	3.3	1	100	30
Relevance of the media to the topic of study	46.7	14	33.3	10	3.3	1	10	3	6.7	2	100	30
Class size	56.7	17	26.7	8	10	3	3.3	1	3.3	1	100	30
Environmental constraints	43.3	13	33.3	10	6.7	2	10	3	6.7	2	100	30

KEY

%- Percentage

f - Frequency

With reference to table 1, 79.9% of the respondents agreed that availability of funds determine the preparation and use of media resources. 13.4 % of the respondents disagreed because teachers could get the media resources from the environment without necessarily buying them. However 6.7% of the respondents were undecided. 97.7% of the respondents agreed that experience of the teacher determines the preparation and use of media resources, while 3.3 % of the respondents disagreed. 83.4% of the respondents agreed that support of the teacher by the school administration in purchasing the media resources and providing storage space determines the preparation and use of media resources. 6.6 % of the respondents disagreed, while 10.0% were undecided. 80 % of the respondents agreed that relevance of the media to the objectives of the topic of study determines the preparation and use of media resources. 16.7 % of the respondents disagreed, while 3.3% of the respondents were undecided. 83.4 % of the respondents agreed that class size determines the preparation and use of media resources. 6.6 % of the respondents disagreed while 10% of the respondents were undecided. 76.6 % of the respondents agreed that environmental constraints determine the preparation and use of media resources. 16.7 % of the respondents disagreed while 6.7% of the respondents were undecided. The results concur with those of Abu-Jaber (1987), who argues that funding, equipment, lack of time and knowledge are obstacles to successful technology integration in meeting teachers' technological needs. They are also in agreement with Moore and Hunt (2003), who argues that nature of the teaching tasks, that is, the amount of school subjects taught, the number of students in class, time constrains during planning and the weekly teaching load are also cited as major factors influencing much of what teachers do in their classrooms.

Figure 1: Ways of getting the instructional media that cannot be purchased

According to figure 1, 66.7% of the respondents said that they improvised instructional media that could not be bought, 73.3 % of the respondents borrowed from friends, 40% of the respondents received donations from friends and well-wishers while 50% of the respondents hired from other institutions.

Respondents were asked if they face difficulties in getting local instructional media. 80% agreed while 20% said that they get the resources easily.

Table 2: Frequency and percentage Scores for Reasons for facing difficulties in obtaining local instructional media resources.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 Inadequate funds for hiring and transporting the media resources to school	226	71.5
2 Lack of time to identify where to get the media	217	68.7
3 Inadequate storage space to keep the media resources before and after using them.	102	32.3
4 Uncooperative learners who do not want to participate in getting the resources	212	67.1
5 Hostile surrounding communities chase students when they are looking for the resources in the neighborhood	57	18.0
6 Other teachers do not want learners to get out of the compound because they would consume their lesson time	28	8.8
7 Other teachers feel that the compound would be untidy	15	4.7

Table 2 shows difficulties faced by respondents in getting local instructional media resources. 71.5 % of the respondents argued that they were not able to get enough funds to enable them hire and transport the resources to the venue where they were to be used, as confirmed by 66.7% of the head teachers who were interviewed. 68.7 % of the respondents lacked time to identify places where they could get the resources. 32.3 % of the respondents lacked storage space to keep the media resources before and after using them. 67.1 % of the respondents argued that learners were uncooperative; therefore, they did not want to participate in getting the resources. 18.0 % of the respondents complained of hostile surrounding communities that chased students when they went to look for the resources in the neighborhood. 8.8 % of the respondents said that other teachers did not want learners to get out of

the compound because they would consume their lesson time. 4.7% of the respondents complained that other teachers felt that the compound would be untidy. The results concur with those of Chandra (2005) who revealed that teachers feel they are not prepared to use new types of resources because they don't get them easily. He adds that for a large number of schools, instructional media is an opportunity cost as there are other needs which are given priority hence they are met at the expense of procurement of instructional materials.

Figure 2: Storage rooms

Figure 2 shows places where teachers kept instructional media resources before and after using them. 3.3% of the respondents kept them in the computer rooms, 33.3% of the respondents kept in the school library, 23.3% of the respondents kept in the staff room, 6.7% of the respondents kept in the machinery rooms, 13.3% of the respondents kept in special rooms allocated for keeping the resources, 76.7 % of the respondents kept in classrooms, 3.3 % of the respondents kept in Deputy head teachers' office and 3.3 % kept in the Head teachers' offices. This is a clear indication that very few special rooms were available for displaying and keeping the instructional media resources. The results obtained here concur with those of Asegedom (1998), who reported lack of the required instructional media resources display and storage rooms and failure of school pedagogical centres to make available ones accessible as reasons for teachers' limited use of instructional media.

Participation by learners in making instructional media resources

Learners were asked whether they participate in making the teaching aids or not. 11 % of the respondents agreed that they participated in making the media resources while 89 % of the respondents never participated in making them.

Table 3: Reasons for Participating in making instructional media resources

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 They are able to display their talent and improve on them.	37	86.0
2 They get an opportunity to relax their minds during this time.	15	34.8

According to table 3, the 43 respondents who agreed that they participated in making the instructional media resources were asked to give reasons for participating. 86.0 % of the respondents participated in making them because they were able to display their talents and improve on them while 34.8 % of the respondents said that they were able to relax their minds as they made them.

Table 4: Reasons for not participating in making instructional media resources

Responses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1 Lack of knowledge and skills on how to make the media resources	340	96.5
2 Materials are expensive	214	60.7
3 Lack of time because the 8-4-4 system of education is congested	315	89.4
4 Teachers do not trust learners hence they don't allow them to do it	118	33.5
5 Learners lack the confidence needed to make the media	245	69.6
6 Learners are lazy	315	89.4
7 Learners believe that it is the work of the teachers	215	61.0
8 Teachers believe that they can make them in a better way than the learners therefore they are selfish	201	57.1
9 Teachers give instructions on how to prepare the resources in a harsh way therefore learners keep off to avoid teachers' wrath.	156	44.3

With reference to table 4, the 352 respondents who never participated in making the instructional media resources were asked to give reasons for not participating in making them. 96.5% of the respondents said they lacked knowledge and skills to make the media resources-; 60.7% of the respondents could not afford prices of material used to make the resources-; 89.4 % of the respondents lacked time because of congestion of 8-4-4 system of education-; 33.5% of the respondents claimed that teachers did not trust learners hence they could not allow them to make them-; 69.6 % of the respondents said that learners lacked the confidence needed to make the media resources-; 89.4 % of the respondents said that learners were lazy; 61.0 % of the respondents argued that teachers believed that they could make them in a better way than the learners-; 57.1 % said that learners believed it was the work of the teachers and 44.3 % of the respondents complained that teachers gave instructions on how to prepare the resources in a harsh way therefore learners kept off to avoid teachers' wrath.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, instructional media selection, arrangement and re-arrangement of learning environment, and the use of materials and equipment to promote learning are basic in self-contained classroom. The entire neighbourhood of the school and community resources should be viewed and utilized as a laboratory for student learning to ensure successful integration of media in teaching as supported by (Blyth-Lord, 1991, Farrant, 1981, and Michealis, 1975). Media should be designed, produced, selected, or used as resources to attain specific instructional objectives. That is, objectives should not be tailored to the media; rather, objectives should guide media utilization. The study therefore recommends that the Ministry of Education should forecast and plan to fund secondary schools to enable them purchase enough instructional Media resources for their use. This will actually boost academic performance of students thereby enabling them realise their future dreams. Secondly, the Ministry of Education should conduct refresher courses so as to equip teachers with relevant skills of preparing and using instructional media resources effectively.

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